

Paper for appraisal and reference: **Strengthening Healthcare Cybersecurity: Systematic Review of Awareness and Training approaches**

Section A: Are the results of the review valid?

1. Did the review address a clearly focused question?

Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Can't Tell	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

HINT: An issue can be 'focused' in terms of

- the population studied
- the intervention given
- the outcome considered

Comments: PICOC framework was used to generate the research questions as follow:

Population: This work was identified as useful for healthcare professionals and IT staff in hospitals that operate medical devices. **Problem:** Human-related cybersecurity threats and incidents.

Intervention: To obtain the most relevant approaches and practices in cybersecurity training and awareness to reduce cybersecurity threats and incidents related to the healthcare sector.

Comparison: None

Outcome: Based on the evaluation of the most relevant approaches and practices obtained, an innovative framework is proposed to strengthen the delivery, design, and evaluation of cybersecurity training and awareness in the healthcare sector that integrates a psychological perspective.

Context: Hospital or healthcare settings

2. Did the authors look for the right type of papers?

Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Can't Tell	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

HINT: 'The best sort of studies' would

- address the review's question
- have an appropriate study design (usually RCTs for papers evaluating interventions)

Comments:

Inclusion criteria included: (1) Articles that discuss or analyze cybersecurity training and awareness approaches, practices, frameworks, or models to reduce threats related to the healthcare sector; (2) Publications between April 2015 and April 2025; and (3) Articles written in English.

Exclusion criteria included: (1) Studies that do not reflect cybersecurity training and awareness approaches, practices, frameworks, or models to reduce threats related to the healthcare sector.

Research questions:

RQ1: What are the most relevant approaches and practices in cybersecurity training and awareness management to reduce cybersecurity threats related to the healthcare sector?

RQ2:Regarding the approaches and practices obtained in cybersecurity awareness training, which ones are standardized, what types of threats do they focus on, what security dimensions do they address, and what effectiveness metrics do they rely on?

Conclusion:

The research questions are related and coincide with the inclusion and exclusion criteria considered.

Is it worth continuing?

3. Do you think all the important, relevant studies were included?

Yes	X
Can't Tell	
No	

HINT: Look for

- which bibliographic databases were used
- follow up from reference lists
- personal contact with experts
- unpublished as well as published studies
- non-English language studies

Comments: The review searched (1) Springer Link; (2) Scopus; (3) ACM Digital Library; (4) IEEEExplore; (5) PubMed; (6) Google Scholar, and grey literature but didn't include non-English studies, the appropriate keywords were used and snowballing process was executed to expand the results of findings.

4. Did the review's authors do enough to assess quality of the included studies?

Yes	X
Can't Tell	
No	

HINT: The authors need to consider the rigour of the studies they have identified. Lack of rigour may affect the studies' results ("All that glisters is not gold" Merchant of Venice – Act II Scene 7)

Comments: The review used the ROBINS-I (Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Interventions) tool, and provided a table summarizing the risk of bias for each study, having the following summary of the risks of bias: serious (2), Moderate to serious (3), Moderate (13), Low to Moderate (5).

5. If the results of the review have been combined, was it reasonable to do so?

Yes	X
Can't Tell	
No	

HINT: Consider whether

- results were similar from study to study
- results of all the included studies are clearly displayed
- results of different studies are similar
- reasons for any variations in results are discussed

Comments: Meta-analysis was not performed because the studies comprising the SLR did not include adequate quantitative data. While some studies presented descriptive statistics, these were not accompanied by the required detailed statistical measures (e.g., sample sizes, effect sizes, confidence intervals, variability measures) and empirical rigor. The studies' focus remained on thematic analysis and qualitative synthesis of findings, coupled with the heterogeneity of the included studies, which limited their suitability for meta-analysis. However, regarding the approaches and practices obtained from cybersecurity awareness training studies, based on standards and best practices, we find the relevant frameworks and the most common: types of threats they focus on, the security dimensions they address, their state of standardization, and the effectiveness metrics on which they are based.

Section B: What are the results?

6. What are the overall results of the review?

HINT: Consider

- If you are clear about the review's 'bottom line' results
- what these are (numerically if appropriate)
- how were the results expressed (NNT, odds ratio etc.)

Comments: The final results of the review are clear regarding the frameworks and other categories of approaches (traditional, technology-based, and innovative training methods) for cybersecurity awareness and training in the healthcare sector and they were quantified in the following:

- a) Frameworks (5),
- b) Other categories of approaches (Traditional Training Methods (6), Technology-Based Training (6) and Innovative Training Methods (1))

In relation with the Common Threats, Security dimensions, and Effectiveness metrics Across Training Methods, were obtained 2 Types of Threats, 3 Security Dimensions and 3 effectiveness Metrics and related to the List of training methods standardization status, were found 2 Fully standardized, 6 Partially standardized and 5 Non-standardized training methods.

Reference: Table 3 to Table 7 from study

Clear results

7. How precise are the results?

HINT: Look at the confidence intervals, if given

Comments: It is a qualitative study and cannot be quantified; however, it is quite accurate because it followed a formal SLR process based on Kitchenham.

Section C: Will the results help locally?

8. Can the results be applied to the local population?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
Can't Tell	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

- HINT: Consider whether
- the patients covered by the review could be sufficiently different to your population to cause concern
 - your local setting is likely to differ much from that of the review

Comments: The review focused on healthcare professionals and IT staff in hospitals that operate medical devices, but the results have not been tested locally, however it has been considered for future work in which a framework will be created and tested with a local population.

9. Were all important outcomes considered?

Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Can't Tell	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

- HINT: Consider whether
- there is other information you would like to have seen

Comments: The review included Frameworks and Other categories of approaches related to technological and psychological perspectives and all reviewed articles have been obtained following a formal process.

10. Are the benefits worth the harms and costs?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
Can't Tell	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>

- HINT: Consider
- even if this is not addressed by the review, what do **you** think?

Comments: The review mentions the most relevant approaches, practices, and models for cybersecurity awareness and training in the healthcare sector, but does not address potential harms or costs.

Summary of CASP Evaluation

Strengths: Clear research question, appropriate study types, quality assessment and the study followed a formal methodology.

Weaknesses: (1) Potential bias from excluding non-English studies; (2) missing cost-effectiveness data, and lack of discussion on harms; (3) the articles that remained inaccessible could have limited this study.

Overall: The SLR is mostly robust but could have limitations in its application in a local population